

At higher concentrations of gelatin sols, greater amounts remain dissolved giving rise to greater number of both aggregated and simple molecules and consequently there is a greater lowering of surface tension.

At the isoelectric point, the gelatin is at a maximum degree of aggregation and thus shows a maximum lowering of surface tension. The greater amount of acid may dissolve greater amounts of colloidal material and consequently there will be a greater number of simple molecules with the result that the surface tension values will not be lowered to a greater extent. High concentrations of acids depress dissociation of the aggregated molecules that are formed and the depression of surface tension will again be higher. The results obtained with 0.5%, 1% and 2% sols of gelatin support this conclusion. Ackermann (*Kolloid Z.*, 1934, 69, 87) has observed that the surface tension of a gelatin sol decreases when the sol is boiled but it is raised by hydrolysis with acid. These observations are in line with the views given above.

The effect of alkali is to increase the surface tension continuously with the increasing concentration of alkali and the effect of solutions of different concentrations of monovalent salts in lowering the surface tension follows the order : $\text{Na} > \text{NH}_4 > \text{Li} > \text{K}$ in the case of gelatin sol.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF SAUGAR,
SAGAR.

Received June 23, 1952.

STUDIES IN SURFACE TENSION MEASUREMENTS OF SOME COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS. PART III. TANNIC ACID, VANADIUM PENTOXIDE, ZIRCONIUM HYDROXIDE AND FERRIC HYDROXIDE SOLS

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The surface tensions of tannic acid and of such hydrated and viscous sols as those of vanadium pentoxide, zirconium hydroxide and ferric hydroxide have been investigated at different concentrations and temperatures, both in presence and absence of electrolytes.

The experimental results indicate that the lowering of surface tension of water in the presence of a colloidal substance originates from the presence of sufficient number of dissolved polaric and aggregated molecules.

In parts I and II of this series of papers (Banerji, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 270; 1953, 30, 133), the results have been explained from the point of view that the reversible colloids such as gelatin, gum arabic etc. have some dissolved material in molecular condition under the equilibrium : simple molecules $\rightleftharpoons$ aggregated molecules $\rightleftharpoons$ colloidal particles.

In this paper, the surface tensions of tannic acid and of such hydrated and viscous sols as those of vanadium pentoxide, zirconium hydroxide and ferric hydroxide have been investigated at different concentrations and temperatures, both in presence and the absence of electrolytes.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental procedure was the same as in the previous papers (*loc. cit.*).

Tannic Acid Sol.—A pure Kahibaun's sample of tannic acid was used. γ stands for surface tension in dynes/cm.

TABLE I
Effect of concentration at 30°.

Conc. (%)	...	1.0	0.5	0.25	0.125
γ	...	70.70	71.45	72.21	73.10

TABLE II
Effect of temperature.

Temp.	...	1 % sol			2 % sol			60°
		30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	
γ	...	70.70	70.15	69.60	67.05	65.90	64.55	63.11

TABLE III
Effect of diff. conc. of HCl and NaOH on the surface tension of a 2% tannic acid sol at 30°.

Sol (40 c.c.)	+ 10 c.c. water	γ .	Sol (40 c.c.)	+ 10 c.c. water	γ .
..	+ 10 0.765 N-HCl	66.43	..	+ 10 1.09N-NaOH	70.61
..	+ 10 N/38.25 ..	68.13	..	+ 10 N/45.87 ..	69.25
..	+ 10 N/382.5 ..	69.23	..	+ 10 N/458.7 ..	67.66
..	+ 10 N/765 ..	70.91	..	+ 10 N/917.4 ..	66.92

TABLE IV
Effect of diff. salt solns. on the surface tension of a 2% tannic acid sol at 30°.

40 c.c. sol.	+ 10 c.c. water	γ .	40 c.c. sol.	+ 10 c.c. N-NH ₄ Cl	γ .
40	.. + .. N-LiCl	67.90	40	.. + .. 1.253 N-CaCl ₂	69.23
40	.. + .. N-NaCl	69.00	40	.. + .. N-BaCl ₂	68.90
40	.. + .. N-KCl	69.90			

TABLE V
Effect of conc. of diff. sols and temperature (of sol A) on surface tension (γ in dynes per cm.).

	γ at concentration of sol at 30°.				γ at temp. (of sol A) at		
	A.	A/2	A/4.	A/8.	40°.	50°.	60°.
V ₂ O ₅	72.25	72.54	72.84	73.20	71.15	69.72	67.90
ZrO ₂	71.85	72.42	72.95	73.55	70.55	69.11	67.93
Fe ₂ O ₃	72.00	72.10	72.20	72.30	70.93	69.46	67.92

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.—The sol was prepared by precipitating vanadic acid from ammonium vanadate by the action of concentrated HCl and then washing the precipitate till it had a tendency to pass to a colloidal state. The whole of the precipitate was then shaken with distilled water and the sol thus formed was allowed to dialyse till it was free from chloride ion. Dialysed sol A = 5.82 g. of V_2O_5 per litre (Table V).

Zirconium Hydroxide Sol.—The sol was prepared from Kahlbaum's sample of zirconium nitrate in the usual way and subsequently purified by dialysis. Dialysed sol A = 9.65 g. of ZrO_2 per litre (Table V).

Ferric Hydroxide Sol.—The sol was prepared by dropping ferric chloride slowly to boiling water and dialysing it. Dialysed sol A = 26.745 g. of F_2O_3 per litre (Table V).

D I S C U S S I O N

The results with tannic acid sol show that the greater the concentration of the sol, the higher the lowering of surface tension. The surface tension also continuously decreases with temperature and with the increasing concentration of acid. On the other hand, the surface tension increases continuously with the increasing concentration of alkali. These results are in general accord with those of gelatin and can be explained from the views already advanced and also mentioned in the beginning of this paper.

The effect of normal solutions of salts in lowering the surface tension follows the order: $Li > Na > NH_4 > K$ in the case of tannic acid.

It is probable that the solubility of tannic acid being very small, the colloidal material gives a greater number of aggregated molecules with the greater amount of acid, whilst the alkali has a tendency to simplify the colloidal particles. Adsorption being greater in the case of aggregated molecules, the lowering of surface tension is higher.

The results with the sols of vanadium pentoxide and zirconium hydroxide show that they have very little effect in lowering the surface tension of water and behave like ferric hydroxide sol although they are supposed to be hydrated (Table V).

Milner's formula (*Phil. Mag.*, 1907, vi, 13, 96) connecting the surface tension of solutions and their concentrations, has been found to apply very well to the colloidal solutions of gelatin, tannic acid, etc. of various concentrations. It may be pointed out here that Johlin (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, 87, 319) believes that a relationship exists between surface tension and concentration of gelatin solution and this relationship is comparable to that obtained in solutions of surface-active substances of low molecular weight. That the colloidal sols above investigated contain at least a portion of them as dissolved materials is borne out by the above consideration.

Dhar and co-workers (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 120) suggest that the drop in the surface tension values of lyophilic colloids is associated with their high values of viscosity and hydration. Frieschmann (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1935, B29, 328), on the

other hand, is of opinion that solvation of dissolved particles such as ions makes the inorganic salts surface-inactive.

The results show that the lowering of surface tension of water in the presence of colloidal substances is not due to high hydration and viscosity of dispersed particles but originates from the presence of a sufficient number of a dissolved polaric and aggregated molecules.

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Received June 23, 1952